

INFLUENCE OF MARKETING MIX STRATEGIES ON PROMOTING COMMUNITY'S TRANSITION FROM CHARCOAL TO CLEAN COOKING ENERGY IN MBEYA CITY

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Abstract: The study examined the influence of marketing mix strategies on community's transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City, with a specific focus on product features. A descriptive research design using a mixed-method approach was employed. Quantitative data were collected through a simple random sample of 100 households from a target population of 133,766 households using clean cooking energy, while qualitative data were obtained from 22 purposively selected key informants. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, while qualitative data were analyzed thematically. The findings indicated that product features positively influenced households' transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy. Respondents expressed favorable perceptions toward both the products and the transition process, with mean scores of 3.89 and 3.90, respectively. Low variance values (.652 and .556) reflected consistent views, while acceptable skewness and kurtosis values confirmed normal data distribution. The study recommends enhancing the design and quality of clean cooking devices to improve durability, usability, and maintenance. Manufacturers should ensure cultural compatibility, ease of use, local technical support, and spare-part availability. Product innovation should prioritize safety and performance standards to build user confidence. Further research should explore long-term adoption trends, environmental and economic impacts, gender dynamics, and policy effectiveness in promoting sustainable clean cooking programs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Clean cooking energy is as cooking fuels and technologies that produce minimal air pollution, reduce health risks, and have a lower environmental impact compared to traditional biomass fuels like charcoal and firewood (WHO, 2024). Clean cooking energy sources include liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), biogas, electricity, ethanol, and improved biomass stoves that enhance fuel efficiency and reduce emissions. These alternatives promote sustainability, improve indoor air quality, and contribute to environmental conservation by reducing deforestation and carbon emissions.

Traditional cooking fuels, particularly charcoal and firewood, pose significant environmental and health challenges globally. Approximately 2.8 billion people rely on solid fuels for cooking which leads to severe air pollution and contributes to climate change (WHO, 2024). Charcoal consumption is a major driver of deforestation, resulting in biodiversity loss and increased greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the World Health Organization (WHO) indicates that 3.2 million people die annually from illnesses linked to indoor air pollution caused by these fuels. The transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy is crucial for sustainable development, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where many households rely on traditional biomass fuels despite their inefficiencies, harmful emissions, and environmental impact (Schlag & Zuzarte, 2018).

Oyenyiran Dauda, Rufai, Surakat. (2025) The transition to clean cooking energy is crucial for improving human health, promoting environmental sustainability, and fostering socio-economic development, particularly in developing countries. A study analysing data from the General Household Survey (2015–2016 and 2018–2019) in Nigeria examines the factors influencing household cooking fuel transitions using a multinomial logistic regression model. In Tanzania, charcoal is the primary cooking fuel for around 90% of households, deeply ingrained in cultural practices. The government has established ambitious targets to transition to cleaner cooking solutions, aiming for 80% of households to adopt these alternatives by 2032 (Ministry of Energy, Tanzania. 2024). Despite this commitment, several barriers impede progress, including cultural preferences for charcoal-cooked food, economic constraints, and limited awareness of the benefits of clean cooking technologies. Initiatives like the Cook Fund program are emerging to raise awareness and promote individual responsibility regarding the environmental impacts of charcoal use (Ministry of Energy, Tanzania 2024).

Mbeya City exemplifies the challenges faced in transitioning from charcoal to clean cooking energy. Many residents, especially food vendors, depend on charcoal for cooking, exposing them to health risks due to smoke inhalation. Although there are initiatives to promote clean cooking alternatives such as gas stove, the uptake remains low (Mugisha & Mwaipopo, 2020). The transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy is essential for achieving environmental sustainability and improving public health. Clean energy product such as solar, biogas, and electric stoves—play a crucial role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, and indoor air pollution. Globally, the International Energy Agency (IEA) reported that renewable energy contributed nearly 30% of total electricity generation in 2020, showing progress toward sustainable energy adoption (IEA, 2021). In Africa, where dependence on traditional biomass fuels remains high, developing and distributing efficient clean cooking products is vital for promoting sustainable land use. The African Union’s target of sourcing 60% of the continent’s energy from renewables by 2030 underscores the growing importance of clean cooking technologies designed to meet the needs of local communities (African Union, 2014).

Tanzania has made notable strides in promoting clean cooking products as part of its renewable energy agenda. Projects such as the Njombe solar power initiative and government-led programs supporting clean cooking devices demonstrate efforts to reduce charcoal use and improve energy access (Tanzania Renewable Energy Association, 2020). These initiatives focus on developing affordable, durable, and user-friendly cooking technologies. By prioritizing innovation, cultural compatibility, and accessibility, clean cooking products can accelerate the country’s transition to sustainable energy and strengthen environmental resilience.

Research objective

To assess the influence of product features on promoting the community’s transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

The study used Marketing Mix Theory (4Ps Model) which developed by Jerome McCarthy (1960) as a framework for businesses to strategically market their products and services. The model consists of Product, Price, Place, and Promotion, which interact to influence consumer decision-making. In the context of promoting the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City, this theory was relevant as it helped in structuring marketing strategies that effectively position clean energy solutions in the market. By ensuring the right product of clean cooking energy was available at the right place of distribution, at a reasonable price, and with proper promotional efforts (advertisement), the transition process can be facilitated, encouraging adoption within the community. Despite its strengths in providing a structured approach to marketing, the 4Ps model has limitations, particularly in the service industry. Scholars like Kotler and Keller (2016) expanded it to 7Ps by adding Process, People, and Physical Evidence to address the unique challenges of service marketing. Additionally, Kotler (1986) suggested the inclusion of public opinion formation and political power, highlighting the evolving nature of marketing strategies. For this study, the 4Ps model guided the formulation of marketing mix strategies by ensuring clean cooking energy solutions were aligned with consumer needs (Product), ultimately promoting the community’s shift from charcoal to clean energy sources. This theory was highly relevant to the study on ‘Assessing the influence of marketing mix strategies on promoting community's transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya city’, As it provides a structured approach to understanding how different marketing mix strategies can drive the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy. Specifically, product help to make comparison base on the durability to make clean

energy solutions more readily available. By applying the 4Ps model, this study assessed how strategic marketing mix interventions can facilitate the transition from charcoal to cleaner cooking alternatives in Mbeya City.

Also, Diffusion of Innovation Theory (Everett Rogers, 1962) was used which explain how new ideas, technologies, or practices spread within a social system over time. The theory originated from communication and sociology studies, where Rogers synthesized research on how innovations such as agricultural practices and technologies were adopted among farmers. He proposed that adoption follows a process influenced by five characteristics of innovation: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. In the context of this study, the theory is relevant because the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City represents the adoption of a new technology. The way households perceive the advantages of clean cooking energy compared to charcoal, its compatibility with their lifestyle, the ease of use, the ability to test it before full adoption, and the visibility of its benefits all play a critical role in influencing their decision to switch. This makes the theory a strong complement to the Marketing Mix Theory, as it provides a behavioral lens for understanding how marketing strategies can accelerate the community's shift to clean energy.

Empirical Literature Review

Ochieng et al. (2019) examined the determinants of household adoption of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) in urban Ghana. The study focused on the role of product characteristics in the switch from biomass to clean fuels. Findings revealed that households were more likely to adopt LPG if the stove was compact, had multiple burners, was fuel-efficient, and came with safety features. The research concluded that beyond affordability, the physical and functional features of clean cooking devices played a central role in influencing adoption behavior. It recommended that stove manufacturers and energy service providers focus on design innovation to improve functionality, convenience, and user safety, which are essential for encouraging the transition to cleaner energy sources.

Niyonshuti and Mushinzimana (2021) conducted a study titled "Socio-economic Aspects Influencing Rural Household Adoption of Improved Clean Cook Stoves: Case Study: Rwanda" published in the American Journal of Modern Energy. The study aimed to identify socio-economic factors affecting the adoption of improved clean cook stoves in rural Rwanda. The study found that product features such as design compatibility with traditional cooking practices, safety, and affordability were critical determinants of adoption. Households were more likely to adopt cookstoves that aligned with their customary cooking methods, ensured user safety, and were cost-effective. The authors recommended that stakeholders consider these product features when promoting improved cookstove technologies to enhance adoption rates. These studies underscore the importance of aligning product features with user needs and preferences to facilitate the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy. By focusing on durability, efficiency, usability, safety, and cultural compatibility, stakeholders can enhance the adoption of clean cooking technologies in various communities.

Musomba et al. (2020) carried out a study on the adoption of improved cook stoves in peri-urban communities in Kenya. The study investigated the factors influencing the uptake of improved cookstoves as alternatives to traditional charcoal and firewood. One of the main findings was that product design features such as size, fuel efficiency, ease of maintenance, and cooking speed significantly influenced user decisions to adopt the stoves. Households preferred stoves that could cook traditional meals quickly and fit into existing kitchen spaces. The research emphasized that products aligned with users' cultural cooking habits and household needs were more likely to be adopted. It recommended that clean cooking energy programs focus on customizing product features to match consumer preferences and improving durability and safety to gain community trust.

Johnsson and Lund (2014) conducted a study titled "Urban Improved Cookstove Adoption – A Study in Tanzanian Urban Areas". The research focused on identifying key drivers and barriers for the adoption of improved cookstoves (ICS) in urban areas of Tanzania, specifically in Dar es Salaam and Moshi. The study found that households were more likely to adopt ICS when the stoves were perceived to be of good quality, durable, and offered fuel savings. However, a significant barrier identified was the poor quality of many ICS models available in the market, which led to scepticism among potential users. The study emphasized the importance of introducing standards to improve the quality of ICS models and facilitate consumers' choice of cook stove. This aligns with the findings of Ochieng et al. (2019), highlighting that beyond affordability, the physical and functional features of clean cooking devices play a central role in influencing adoption behaviour.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This framework established a clear relationship between independent variable (marketing mix strategies which is product) that manipulated/analyzed and dependent variables (transition to clean cooking energy) which measured to assess the effectiveness of the independent variables.

Source: Developed by Researcher, 2025.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for Assessing Influence of Marketing Mix Strategies in Promoting Community’s Transition from Charcoal to Clean Cooking Energy.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Mbeya City, which is located at southern highland region Tanzania, it has approximately a population of 541,603 in all 36 wards and it was a rapidly growing urban centre in the southern highlands of the country (NBS, 2023). Mbeya City serves as a major commercial and transport hub, with a diverse population engaged in various economic activities. Despite its urban development, a significant portion of households (Approximately 75.3%) still relied on charcoal as their primary cooking fuel, posing environmental and health risks (TFS,2020).

Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were used in this study because different types of data were collected and analysed separately. The quantitative approach focused on gathering numerical data that can be statistically measured and analysed, while the qualitative approach captured descriptive information to provide deeper insights into participants’ views and experiences.

The study used a descriptive research design because it aimed to understand and describe the influence of marketing mix strategies on promoting the community's transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City. Specifically, the descriptive research design was profiling the influence of product in promoting community’s transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City.

The study population comprised households in Mbeya City, particularly those using clean cooking energy as their primary cooking fuel. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2023), Mbeya City has a total population of 541,603, yet only 24.7%, or 133,776 people, use clean cooking energy. This highlights a significant reliance on traditional cooking fuels, necessitated further research on strategies to promote the adoption of clean energy solutions. Additionally, key stakeholders involved in promoting clean cooking energy, such as local government officials (100), energy providers (10), and community leaders (40), were also included to provide comprehensive insights.

The study employed both probability and non-probability sampling technique where by probability sampling (simple random sampling) was used for obtaining a sample of 100 households from Mbeya City for collecting quantitative data so as to ensure that each member of the target population has an equal chance of being selected. Also, non-probability sampling (purposive sampling) was used in obtaining sample of 22 key informant for collecting qualitative data. The method allowed a researcher to deliberately select individuals based on their knowledge, experience, and relevance to the study. Their respective population and sample selected is shown in table below.

Table 1: Sample size for key informants

Stakeholder Group	Estimated Population	Sample
Local government officials	100	10
Energy providers	10	5
Community leaders	40	7
Total	150	22

Source: Research findings, (2025)

The study utilized primary data to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the influence of the marketing mix on promoting community’s transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City. Data are facts, figures, and other relevant materials, both past and present that serve as the basis for study and analysis (Mlyuka, 2015). These data are collected first-hand through various methods to ensure accuracy and relevance. In this study, primary data were collected from households in Mbeya City by using questionnaire for collecting quantitative data and semi-structured interview for key informant in obtaining qualitative data so as to assess their perceptions and behaviours regarding the influence of marketing mix strategies specifically product in adoption of clean cooking energy.

Data analysis is the process of evaluating data using analytical and logical reasoning to examine each component of the data provided. Data from various sources is gathered, reviewed, and then analysed to form some sort of finding or conclusion (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2016). SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 25 were used for quantitative data, Since the study was guided by research questions rather than hypotheses, the primarily data were analysed by descriptive analysis to summarize and interpret the data, (such as frequencies, means, and percentages) which examined the influence of marketing mix strategies (product features) on promoting community’s transition to clean cooking energy. The qualitative collected from key informant interviews and open-ended responses were analysed using thematic analysis. This method involved identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns or themes within the data. The process was beginning with the transcription of interviews, followed by familiarization with the data through repeated readings.

To enhance validity, a pilot study was conducted by testing a sample of questions before proceeding to full-scale data collection. Furthermore, the research instruments reviewed by experts and peers for feedback and improvements. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test used to assess the adequacy of the sampling. Additionally, pre-testing of questionnaires conducted, and based on the results, necessary modifications were made before final distribution to the target population.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.843
	Approx. Chi-Square	1362.352
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Df	325
	Sig.	.000

Source: Research findings, (2025)

According to Table 2, the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity showed that the data variables obtained after the data reduction process were significant (0.000) to measure the dependent variable with a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value of 0.843 in accordance to Kaiser who states that the results from factor analysis can be considered acceptable if the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value (KMO) is 0.5 or greater, and the Bartlett’s test of sphericity is statistically significant, $p < 0.05$ therefore the Factor Analysis is valid, hence the researcher is confident that factor analysis is appropriate for these data.

The study used Cronbach’s Alpha (α) analysis to test the reliability of the predictor variables. A Cronbach’s Alpha value below 0.60 was considered as indicating poor reliability, necessitating adjustments to improve the measurement tool.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Based on	N of Item
Product	.762		4
Transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy.	.755		5

Source: Research Findings, (2025)

According to Table 3 shows that every construct had acceptable to good internal consistency. The variables had Cronbach's Alpha scores in particular, Product ($\alpha = 0.762$), and Transition to Clean Cooking Energy ($\alpha = 0.755$), the findings indicate that the questionnaire's items were dependable and appropriate for additional examination. The measurement tool did not need to be adjusted because no constructs recorded values below the 0.60 threshold.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations play a crucial role in research, as participants' privacy and confidentiality must be safeguarded. In this study, the researcher ensured the anonymity of respondents and maintain confidentiality of the information provided. No respondent's identity disclosed in any part of the research findings. Moreover, participants were given the freedom to provide information voluntarily without coercion. The researcher seek approval for data collection by obtaining an official introduction letter from postgraduate directorate of the university. Throughout the data collection process, ethical guidelines were strictly observed to protect respondents' rights and ensure credibility of the study.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the findings related to the study. The findings from both descriptive statistics and qualitative responses obtained from the respondents. The analysis focuses on packaging differentiation, frequency of repairs or breakdown and ease of finding replacement parts locally. Respondents were given four statements to rate on a Likert scale of agreement. In table 4 statements and their responses are displayed.

Table 4: The influence of product features on promoting the community's transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy

Statement	SD		D		N		A		SA		Total
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Using clean cooking products leads to significant cost savings compared to using charcoal or firewood due to packaging differentiation	5	5	8	8	10	10	40	40	37	37	100
Clean cooking products require fewer repairs or breakdowns compared to traditional cooking methods.	4	4	14	14	11	11	47	47	24	24	100
It is easy to find replacement parts for clean cooking products locally.	2	2	17	17	19	19	48	48	14	14	100
The durability of clean cooking products meets my expectations.	1	1	2	2	18	18	53	53	26	26	100

Source: Field data (2025)

The study found that product-related attributes strongly influence the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City. The majority of respondents perceived clean cooking products as cost-effective, durable, and low-maintenance, with 77% noting cost savings, 71% highlighting fewer repairs, 74% reporting easy access to replacement parts, and 79% satisfied with product durability. In addition to quantitative data, qualitative information was collected to supplement these findings and provide deeper insights into the reasons behind respondents' perceptions.

One respondent noted:

“Packaging has a direct influence on the customer on the transition from charcoal to the use of clean cooking energy because the different packaging gives a different option with a different price that might be reliable and affordable for the product, so it is true that a person can prefer to use the clean cooking energy based on the different packaging”. (Energy provider no. 1, 7/13/25 11:02:33)

Another respondent explained:

“The package is the first thing I look at since it indicates whether the product is useful for my house. I hesitate if it seems heavy or unreliable. But confidence is boosted when the product is packaged neatly, is easy to store, and comes with clear instructions. When clean cooking energy is packaged well, it feels more approachable and contemporary, which motivates individuals like me to abandon charcoal, particularly if the packaging conveys that it is simple to maintain.” (Community leader no. 1, 7/13/25 13:42:54)

Energy Provider explained:

“Users express concerns regarding delays or restricted access to fuel refills, particularly in rural regions. This deters ongoing adoption of clean cooking technologies. Maintenance poses a challenge as individuals often claim they lack the knowledge to address small problems, and professional repair services are not consistently accessible or cost-effective. Regarding durability, some claim that stoves fail too quickly, especially the burner or regulator components, leading them back to using charcoal. To facilitate the transition, multiple initiatives have been launched, including training programs aimed at instructing users on proper stove usage and fundamental troubleshooting. Mobile refuelling stations and local agents have been established in isolated regions to enhance fuel accessibility. Furthermore, several energy suppliers currently provide warranties and post-purchase assistance to promptly resolve malfunctions, increasing users' trust in utilizing clean cooking options.” (Energy Provider no. 3, 7/16/25 14:02:30)

Qualitative insights emphasized that packaging, reliability, and ease of use further motivate adoption, though challenges remain in fuel accessibility and local repair services. Overall, enhancing product quality, support services, and local availability is key to accelerating the shift to clean cooking solutions.

The findings of the study showing strong respondent agreement that clean cooking products save cost, require fewer repairs, offer accessible replacement parts, and meet expectations for durability align with recent empirical literature emphasizing the centrality of product reliability and local maintenance support in adoption dynamics. For example, in Wereta, Ethiopia, Ashagrie et al. (2024) found that households cited concerns over repair difficulty, product lifespan, and maintenance costs as important barriers to adopting improved charcoal cookstoves.

Another relevant study is “Evaluation of the Preference for and Viability of Clean Cookstove Adoption in Rural Tanzania” (Katikiro et al., 2023), which found that although many rural households stacked fuels like firewood, charcoal, kerosene, or LPG, the aggregate cost of LPG was less than daily expenditures on charcoal or firewood. This supports our respondents' views about cost savings one of the product attributes we measured.

These studies provide support for the conclusion that product features are not peripheral but foundational to clean cooking energy adoption. Durability (fewer breakdowns), ease of obtaining spare parts locally, and packaging that reduces cost burden or improves cost visibility by reduce perceived risk and contribute to sustained usage. Policymakers and manufacturers should prioritize designing clean cooking products with these features in mind, ensure local spare part supply chains are developed, and package products and fuel in units that match household budgets, to enhance adoption and sustained use.

There is less published data so far specifically on packaging differentiation and local spare-part access, but related initiatives in Tanzania in 2025 suggest innovations in product design and service models are emerging. For example, Mama Mia's Soko and Smartpika Limited were recognized for designing LPG canisters and electric pressure cookers with Pay-As-You-Go (PAYGO) systems that make appliances more accessible and reliable in use. Such innovations address several of your product variables especially affordability in the long run via reduced repair frequency, and improved product reliability.

Thus, findings reinforce that product attributes are not just peripheral; they are central to clean cooking adoption. Without product reliability (durability, fewer breakdowns), even awareness or affordability may not lead to sustained use. Also, easy access to spare parts helps reduce perceived risk, which is often a major barrier when households switch from familiar fuels like charcoal.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the central tendency and dispersion of responses regarding the influence of marketing mix strategies (product,) and the transition to clean cooking energy. Table 5 presents the number of respondents (N), minimum and maximum values, mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis for each key variable.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Error	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis		
								Statistic	Statistic	
PRODUCT	100	1.25	5.00	3.8900	.08074	.652	-.596	.241	.448	.478
TRANSITIONTOCLEANCOOKINGENERGY	100	2.00	5.00	3.9000	.07454	.556	-.433	.241	.166	.478
Valid N (listwise)	100									

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics for the study variables. The analysis included 100 participants with complete responses. The mean scores for product (M = 3.89) and transition to clean cooking energy (M = 3.90) indicate that participants generally rated these items positively. Both variables exhibited low variance (product = 0.081, transition to clean cooking energy = 0.075), suggesting that responses were relatively consistent across participants. Skewness values were slightly positive for product (0.652) and transition to clean cooking energy (0.556),

reflecting a modest asymmetry towards higher ratings. Similarly, kurtosis values were slightly negative (product = -0.596, transition to clean cooking energy = -0.433), indicating distributions that are somewhat flatter than a normal distribution. Overall, the data show generally high and consistent ratings with minor deviations from normality.

The descriptive statistics demonstrate a generally positive influence of the marketing mix strategies in influencing the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy. The central tendency and shape of the data distributions indicate that most respondents rated these strategies highly, suggesting they play a significant role in shaping energy choices within the community.

6. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that marketing mix strategies, particularly the product component, play a significant role in promoting the transition from charcoal to clean cooking energy in Mbeya City. High-quality, durable, and user-friendly products were identified as key factors in increasing household satisfaction and encouraging adoption, as they required fewer repairs and offered reliable performance over time. The availability of spare parts locally further reinforced product reliability and convenience, making it easier for households to maintain and continue using clean cooking solutions. Despite these positive outcomes, the study found that adoption remains uneven, with some households only partially transitioning due to financial constraints, habits, or lack of awareness. Overall, the findings underscore that a comprehensive marketing mix combining high-quality, accessible products is essential for accelerating the shift to clean cooking energy, improving household well-being, and contributing to sustainable energy goals in urban Tanzania.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

To promote the adoption of clean cooking energy, products should be well designed to enhance their quality, durability, and ease of use, ensuring they effectively meet household needs. Manufacturers should also ensure that spare parts and technical support are readily available at the local level, enabling users to maintain and repair their appliances conveniently. These improvements will strengthen user confidence, improve satisfaction, and reduce barriers to adoption, encouraging more households to shift from charcoal to clean cooking energy. Future initiatives should focus on assessing long-term adoption to understand the sustainability of behavioural change, while also comparing rural and urban contexts to identify differences influenced by income, infrastructure, culture, and access to information. Impact assessments are needed to quantify the environmental, economic, and health benefits of clean cooking technologies, supporting evidence-based policymaking. Moreover, exploring the gender dimension will help tailor programs that reflect women’s critical roles in household energy decisions. Finally, evaluating the effectiveness of current government policies and incentives will inform the refinement of strategies that promote wider and more sustainable use of clean cooking solutions.

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